

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO WORKING WITH TEXT IN IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGICAL PREPARATION OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. *The article discusses the importance of working with text as a means of developing reading literacy in primary school students, teaching the methodology of formulating questions based on textbook texts in accordance with the four cognitive processes, developing the skill of gradually complicating questions based on Bloom's taxonomy, strengthening critical thinking through the "Language of Questions", and implementing creative question-building approaches into practice.*

Keywords: *reading literacy, fact-checking, interpretation and connection, inference, evaluation, test, matching.*

Introduction

As one of the primary objectives of every country around the world, the continuous development of the education system is among the highest priorities of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This is because the prosperity and future of the nation lie in the hands of the young generation who are eager to learn and practice. Along with improving the quality of education, significant attention is also being given to the preparation of qualified and highly skilled pedagogical personnel. In order to develop the education system in our country, a new national program has been created, and based on this program a new generation of textbooks is being published systematically. The quality level of students' acquired knowledge and skills is being assessed not only on the basis of national curriculum requirements, but also through international assessment program standards.

In the context of primary school students' reading skills improvement, developing the text analysis and text comprehension skills creates a foundation for mastering all areas of education more effectively. Therefore, it is appropriate to develop and develop methodological recommendations that assist future primary school teachers working in this field improve their professional skills through new innovative approaches and experiences. One of such innovative approaches is **Bloom's taxonomy**, where the term "**taxonomy**" refers to the principle of arranging the context in a hierarchical order (from lower to higher levels). Bloom's taxonomy is regarded as one of the most significant classification systems of 20th century pedagogy. This concept was developed in 1956 by a group of scholars led by the American psychologist and educationalist **Benjamin Bloom**. The team's primary objective was to identify the levels of cognitive (mental) activity involved in the learning process, organize them in a coherent hierarchy, and thereby enable teachers to plan instructional materials more effectively. Benjamin Bloom categorized educational objectives into three domains: **cognitive, affective, and psychomotor** [2]:

1. **Cognitive** - encompasses skills related to knowledge acquisition, comprehension, and critical thinking. It includes a continuum of activities ranging from becoming acquainted with

information and memorizing it, to practical application of acquired knowledge in order to solve problems.

2. **Affective** - relates to emotions and attitudes, whereby primary purpose is to develop an emotional orientation toward phenomena in the surrounding world. Within this domain, attention is given to how individuals perceive, respond to, and evaluate various life situations, as well as the values, interests, and inclinations of other people.

3. **Psychomotor** - concerns the development of practical skills and focuses on directing the ability to use various tools and techniques toward the achievement of specific objectives [3].

Among the domains outlined above, particular attention is given to the **cognitive domain**. This is because all sequential learning processes are fundamentally grounded in well-established and solidly acquired knowledge. Benjamin Bloom identified **six levels of educational objectives**, arranged in a hierarchical order, each designed to cultivate a specific level of thinking ability. Bloom's taxonomy assists in the accurate formulation of educational objectives, based on which, teachers design learning tasks for students and select appropriate assessment tools. Through the application of the taxonomy, teachers can organize the instructional process in such a way that students not only acquire new knowledge but also learn to analyze it and apply it in real-life contexts.

Bloom's system of objectives is structured from the **simplest to the most complex levels of thinking**. *Remembering* and *understanding* correspond to the lower levels of cognitive development; *application* and *evaluation* represent the intermediate level; whereas *analysis* and *creation* correspond to higher-order thinking skills. According to Bloom, one of the most important responsibilities of a teacher is to guide students toward achieving these higher levels of thinking [4].

1. **Remembering** – the first stage that refers to the recalling and reproducing the information that has been learned. At this level, the learner becomes familiar with key terms, specific facts, and rules, and is able to repeat or recognize them. An overall understanding of the topic starts to form at this stage. To formulate objectives, the following action verbs may be used: *identify, name, recall, organize, list, learn, find, show, write, select*.

2. **Understanding** – the second stage where comprehension and awareness take place. The main indicator of mastering this level is the ability to present the material in one's own words. The learner knows and understands rules and principles, can explain facts and phenomena, and provide commentary on graphs and diagrams. Action verbs: *identify, explain, describe, interpret, compare, summarize, distinguish, give examples, clarify*.

3. **Application** – third stage whose aim is to learn how to apply acquired knowledge in specific contexts. At this level, the learner solves practical problems using new rules, formulas, and laws. Action verbs: *make decisions, distribute, demonstrate, explain, apply, calculate, study, conduct experiments, find, select*.

4. **Analysis** – at the fourth level, the learner's objective is to understand the structure of the material and divide it into its constituent parts. The learner can recognize the principles underlying the creation of information and identify logical inconsistencies or errors. Action verbs: *analyze, emphasize, construct, determine, explain, organize, devise, contrast, differentiate, draw conclusions*.

5. **Synthesis** – upon reaching the fifth level, the learner is able to integrate and consolidate previously acquired knowledge. The learner applies this knowledge to construct new

structures, such as a classification method or a plan for solving a problem. Action verbs: *compose, develop, group, combine, establish, plan, generalize, examine, propose, formulate, analyze.*

6. **Evaluation** – at the highest level, the learner evaluates ideas and concepts using criteria that may be developed independently or with the teacher’s guidance. The primary objective is to assess the logic underlying the construction of the material, verify the validity of conclusions, and justify one’s own viewpoint. Action verbs: *discover, construct, defend, present, discuss, examine, justify, confirm, predict.*

For primary school students, the effectiveness of working with a text largely depends on the questions and tasks selected by the teacher. Bloom’s taxonomy contributes to the development of students’ thinking by gradually increasing the complexity of text analysis. When conducting text analysis through Bloom’s taxonomy, questions and tasks are designed for each level as follows.

Remembering stage - the learner recalls specific facts from the text.

- Who is the main character in the story?
- Where do the events take place?
- What happens at the beginning of the story?
- Find and name an object or feature mentioned in the text.

Understanding stage - the learner is able to explain the content of the text in their own words.

- Briefly explain what the story is about.
- Why did the character act in that way?
- What kind of mood or feeling did this text give you?

Application stage - the learner applies the acquired knowledge in a close situation.

- Describe a similar event from your own life.
- What would you do if you were in the place of the main character?
- How can the moral idea presented in the text be applied in everyday life?

Analysis stage - the learner divides the text into parts and searches for cause–effect relationships.

- Divide the text into three main events.
- What differences exist between the characters?
- Why did the event end in this way?

Synthesis stage – the learner generates a new idea based on the text that has been read.

- Write a new episode as a continuation of the story.
- Compose a poetic cinquain based on the studied text.
- Write a letter to the character.
- Propose an alternative title for the work.

Evaluation stage - the learner forms his own conclusions and is able to express an independent opinion.

- Were the character’s actions correct?
- Why do you think so?
- What is the most important idea expressed in the text?
- What conclusion did you draw from the story?

In primary education, the process of analyzing a literary text through the application of Bloom’s taxonomy can be illustrated using the example of the text “**Qoziq**” by **Otkir Hoshimov**, presented in the Grade 4 *Reading Literacy* textbook.

Methodology for creating the “Question Complexity Spiral” based on Bloom’s taxonomy:

Stage	Question example	Expected skill
Remembering	What grade is a boy in?	Recalling factual information from the text
	Where does the boy take his cow to graze?	Recalling a specific location
	What did he find in the oleaster grove?	Identifying a specific fact
	Where does the boy find the stake?	Recalling the name of a factual element
Understanding	Why does the boy become happy after finding the new stake?	Understanding and explaining the reason
	Why does the boy say, “My heart seemed to pull back”?	Explaining the character’s emotional state
	Why were the family members in the story unable to object to the father?	Interpreting the character portrayal
	Why does the father insist that the boy return the object he found to its place?	Explaining the character’s actions
Application	Give an example of an event similar to the one in the story.	Applying the situation to one’s own life experience
	Would you obey your father’s demands unquestioningly, as the boy does?	Application beyond the text
	What lesson does the father teach his child?	Interpreting the character’s actions
Analysis	Identify the problem in the story and its resolution.	Distinguishing elements of the plot
	Explain the characters of the boy and the father.	Comparing and analyzing the characters
	Explain how the episode describing the oleaster grove is connected to the main idea of the story.	Establishing a link between a detail and the central idea
	What negative consequences might have arisen if the boy had gone to the oleaster grove at night?	Analyzing the character’s actions
Synthesis	If you were in the boy’s place, what would you do?	Developing a new idea
	What title would you give to the story?	Creating a reasoned creative interpretation
	Continue the story with an alternative ending.	Creating a new narrative development

Evaluation	How are the family members' attitude and respect toward the father shown in the story?	Evaluating the characters' actions
	In your opinion, what is the main idea of the story?	Evaluating the main idea and drawing a personal conclusion
	What lesson did you learn from this story?	Integrating and synthesizing the ideas

In conclusion

It may be emphasized that Bloom's taxonomy assists future primary school teachers in designing questions and tasks that progress from simple to more complex levels, thereby enabling students to conduct a comprehensive analysis of a text and fully understand it. Mastering the technology of developing a system of questions and tasks for each stage, organizing them according to the principle of progression from simple to complex, and fostering creative as well as critical thinking contributes to effective text analysis and allows students to gain literary experience through engagement with the text.

Furthermore, students learn not merely to memorize a text, but also to understand, apply, and analyze it. As a result, the learning process becomes active, engaging, and logically structured. Each student develops gradually according to his or her individual abilities. Independent thinking, creativity, and logical reasoning are cultivated. Through the use of multi-level questions, students are encouraged to think more deeply. Accordingly, it is recommended that every teacher organize the instructional process effectively and make efficient use of appropriate technologies and pedagogical methods to achieve these objectives.

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